

Synthesis of some bioactive analogues of phthalein dyes and their anticandidal activity

R. P. Chamoli*^a, Shailendra Prakash^a, D. P. Kothiyal^a and Veena Joshi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Government P. G. College, Gopeshwar-246 101, Uttaranchal, India

E-mail : drpochamoli@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Garhwal University Campus, Tehri-249 145, Uttaranchal, India

Manuscript received 4 January 2000, revised 16 June 2006, accepted 14 July 2006

Abstract : Some new analogues of phthalein dyes have been synthesised which may be regarded as $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolides due to the presence of five membered unsaturated γ -lactone ring in their structures. Evaluation of anticandidal activity reveals that some of the compounds are very active against *Candida albicans*.

Keywords : Phthalein dyes, bioactivity.

In view of the significant biological activities associated with phthaleins¹ and butenolides², it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some analogues of phthalein dyes with α,β -unsaturated butenolactone ring in their structures, and evaluate their anticandidal activity against *Candida albicans*. The resulting compounds are $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolides.

Results and discussion

$\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -Butenolides (**1a-d**) were synthesised by condensing resorcinol with β -benzoylacrylic acid, β -(4-methylbenzoyl) acrylic acid, β -(4-chlorobenzoyl) acrylic acid and β -(4-bromobenzoyl) acrylic acid respectively, in presence of catalytic quantity of concentrated sulphuric acid by the reported procedure³. Compounds (**1a-d**) on bromination, iodination and mercuration gave their corresponding dibromo (**2a-d**), diiodo (**3a-d**) and diacetoxymercuri (**4a-d**) derivatives (Scheme 1). The syntheses of **2a-d** have already been reported³. The syntheses of **3a-d** and **4a-d** are reported in the present communication.

Compounds **1a-d**, **2a-d**, **3a-d** and **4a-d** were evaluated *in vitro* for their antimicrobial activity against *Candida albicans* at a concentration 1 mg/ml using amphotericin B as control. Some of the compounds (**1** and **2**) showed moderate anticandidal activity while the mercurated compounds (**4a-d**) were sufficiently active to be comparable with the control.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of the products was ascertained by TLC. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer.

Diiodo- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolides (3a-d) : Treatment of a solution of **1a-d** in aq. NaOH with a solution of iodine in aq. KI, and subsequent acidification by dil. HCl in usual man-

*Present address : House No. 10, Street No. 2, Ashirwad Enclave, Dehradun-248 001, Uttaranchal, India.

ner afforded **3a-d** as brick-red solid compounds, yield 79–81%; γ -Phenyl- γ -(3,5-diiodo-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **3a**, m.p. 180–182°d (Found : I, 49.2. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4I_2$ requires : I, 48.8%); ν_{\max} 3440, 1785, 1760 and 1620 cm^{-1} ; γ -(4-Methylphenyl)- γ -(3,5-diiodo-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **3b**, m.p. 196–198°d (Found : I, 47.8. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4I_2$ requires : I, 47.5%); ν_{\max} 3440, 1785, 1770 and 1625 cm^{-1} ; γ -(4-Bromophenyl)- γ -(3,5-diiodo-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **3c**, m.p. 210–212°d (Found : I, 42.7. $C_{16}H_9O_4BrI_2$ requires : I, 42.4%); ν_{\max} 3350, 1780, 1760 and 1620 cm^{-1} ; γ -(4-Chlorophenyl)- γ -(3,5-diiodo-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **3d**, m.p. 150–152°d (Found : I, 45.6. $C_{16}H_9O_4ClI_2$ requires : I, 45.8%); ν_{\max} 3440, 1795, 1738 and 1625 cm^{-1} .

Diacetoxymercuri- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolides (4a-d) : These were synthesized as usual by treating a solution of **1a-d** in anhydrous methanol with mercuric acetate dissolved in anhydrous methanol in presence of few drops of glacial acetic acid to get pink/brown solid products (yield 60–67%). γ -Phenyl- γ -(3,5-diacetoxymercuri-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **4a**, m.p. >300°d (Found : Hg, 50.6. $C_{20}H_{16}O_8Hg_2$ requires : Hg, 51.1%); ν_{\max} 3400, 1785, 1750, 1630, 1555 and 1385 cm^{-1} ; γ -(4-methylphenyl)- γ -(3,5-diacetoxymercuri-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **4b**, m.p. 300°d (Found : Hg, 50.0. $C_{21}H_{18}O_8Hg_2$ requires : Hg, 50.2%); ν_{\max} 3400, 1785, 1620, 1580 and 1390 cm^{-1} ; γ -(4-Bromophenyl)- γ -(3,5-diacetoxymercuri-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **4c**, m.p. >300°d

(Found : Hg, 46.1. $C_{20}H_{15}O_8BrHg_2$ requires : Hg, 46.4%); ν_{\max} 3440, 1785, 1745, 1630, 1560 and 1405 cm^{-1} ; γ -(4-Chlorophenyl)- γ -(3,5-diacetoxymercuri-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)- $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -butenolide **4d**, m.p. >300°d (Found : Hg, 48.7. $C_{20}H_{15}O_8ClHg_2$ requires : Hg, 48.9%); ν_{\max} 3400, 1790, 1740, 1625, 1565 and 1402 cm^{-1} .

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. Aalice M. Clark, School of Pharmacy, University of Mississippi, U.S.A., for his generous help in evaluating anticandidal activity. They specially thank Prof. P. C. Gupta for helpful suggestions.

References

1. E. L. Forder, B. A. Luxon and V. S. Sharma, *Am. J. Physiol.*, 1985, **24B**, 702; Douglas C. Neckers, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1987, **64**, 649; P. Camilleri, A. Gray, K. Weaver, J.R. Bower and D. J. Williams, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1989, **37**, 519; Raad Al-Hamdany and Zancharia A. Fataftah, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1997, **9**, 703.
2. Y. S. Rao, *Chem. Rev.*, 1976, **76**, 625; L. Liao, "Synthesis of Biological Interesting Natural Furan-2-ones and Pyran-2-ones : Cerpegin, Yangonin, Hispidin and their Analogues", Ph.D. Thesis, University of Caen, France, 1999; L. Liao and D. Villemin, *J. Chem. Res., Synop.*, 2000, 179; G. Mahaeut, L. Liao, J. M. Catel, P. A. Jaffres and D. Villemin, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 2001, **78**, 654.
3. D. P. Kothiyal and R. P. Chamoli, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1989, **1**, 64; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, **29**, 166; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 69; *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1991, **63**, 209.